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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Antecedentes de la aparición de trastornos emocionales en parejas al borde del divorcio

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Resumen

El matrimonio es un asunto bilateral y complejo entre dos personas, que desempeña un papel esencial en la satisfacción de las necesidades emocionales, psicológicas y físicas de la pareja. Teniendo en cuenta que la comunicación efectiva y la expresión de los sentimientos es el principal factor de diferencia entre las parejas satisfechas e insatisfechas, parece necesario investigar los factores relacionados con los trastornos emocionales en las parejas al borde del divorcio. En el presente estudio, el papel de los trastornos emocionales en los conflictos conyugales se basa en el aspecto psicológico de los Criterios de Dominio de Investigación (RDoC). La presente investigación es cualitativa y se utilizó el enfoque de la teoría fundamentada, que se basa en la experiencia de los entrevistados a lo largo de su vida. Los datos se obtuvieron mediante entrevistas en profundidad con expertos en el campo de la psicología. Los destinatarios de la investigación fueron psicólogos de Teherán. Tras la recogida de datos, se realizó una triangulación en tres niveles de codificación. Los resultados mostraron que la conciencia de estas dimensiones en la vida de cada persona puede prevenir la aparición de trastornos emocionales en las parejas, de hecho, la falta de conciencia de las diferentes dimensiones de las emociones en la vida matrimonial puede crear un círculo vicioso y continuar en la dirección equivocada. Según los resultados de la investigación, parece que si se diseña y aplica un programa adecuado de asesoramiento o tratamiento, es posible prevenir la aparición de daños causados por los antecedentes de los trastornos emocionales, como las emociones negativas, en la vida conyugal de las parejas.

Palabras clave: trastornos emocionales, divorcio, marco RDdC.

Abstract

ANTECEDENTS OF THE OCCURRENCE OF EMOTIONAL DISORDERS IN COUPLES ON THE VERGE OF DIVORCE

Marriage is a two-sided and complex matter between two people, which plays an essential role in meeting the emotional, psychological and physical needs of the couple. Considering that effective communication and expression of feelings is the main factor in the difference between satisfied and dissatisfied couples, therefore, it seems necessary to investigate the factors related to emotional disorders in couples on the verge of divorce. In the current study, the role of emotional disorders in marital conflicts

is based on the psychological aspect of Research Domain Criteria (RDoC). The current research is qualitative and the grounded theory approach is used, which is based on the experience of the interviewees throughout their lives. Data were obtained through in-depth interviews with experts in the field of psychology. The research community were psychologists in Tehran. After data collection, triangulation was done at three levels of coding. The results showed that the awareness of these dimensions in the life of each person can prevent the occurrence of emotional disorders in couples, in fact, the lack of awareness of the different dimensions of emotions in married life can create a vicious cycle and continue in the wrong direction. According to the findings of the research, it seems that if a suitable counseling or treatment program is designed and implemented, it is possible to prevent the occurrence of damages caused by the antecedents of emotional disorders such as negative emotions in the married life of couples.

Keywords: emotional disorders, divorce, RDoC framework

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1. Introduction

Marriage is a two-sided and complex matter between two people, which plays an essential role in providing the emotional, psychological and physical needs, as well as the flourishing of the abilities and mental peace of the couple. This mental peace is achieved when the couple can show the appropriate emotional reaction to the expression of each other's thoughts, desires and behaviors. Couples who suffer from emotional disorders endure a lot of stress and suffering, so their emotional and marital relationships are disturbed and they are more likely to be exposed to psychological fragility, marriage instability and divorce (Abassi, Askarpour and Gharibi, 2018; Fath Elahi et al., 2014). These severe conflicts and differences are among the important factors that negatively affect the quality of married life and the stability of marriage (Thawabi, Khoynejad and Safarian Toosi, 2019). Considering the negative effects and consequences of divorce at the individual and social levels, especially for women, and the significant increase in the number of divorces in Iran in recent years, it is necessary to take preventive measures to reduce these damages. And this is only possible by identifying the factors that create the background of this phenomenon (Damari, Masoudi Farid, Derakhshan Nia and Ehsani Chimeh, 1400).

Various researches consider various factors involved in conflict and tendency towards divorce; But a common factor that has been mentioned in most researches is cognitions, which include attitudes, thoughts and schemas. Schemas are important beliefs and feelings about oneself and the environment that people have accepted without question. One of their types is emotional schemas, based on which emotional disorders are defined, caused by how people evaluate and interpret their emotional experiences and

the strategies they use to deal with them (Zamani Zarchi, Samadi Kashan and Qasimzadeh, 2017). According to the studies, people are different in the way they experience emotions and conceptualize them, and depending on the beliefs they have about their emotions, they choose different ways to act. People who have a lot of negative emotions tend to take extreme actions in relatively anxiety-provoking or unfavorable situations. These people blame and severely criticize themselves and show excessive sensitivity towards others. These negative characteristics, in the long term, cause separation and distance between couples, problems in the relationship and a decrease in intimacy (Weiss, Lavner and Miller, 2017).

In previous studies, the role of emotional disorders in marital conflicts has been investigated from the psychological aspect and based on the ICD-11 and DSM-5 systems. However, according to the RDoC system, emotional disorders are not just derived from cognitive and mental disorders and have a psycho-biological basis. The difference in the theoretical framework of RDoC regarding the investigation of emotional disorders is the correction and change in the continuity and similarity of the signs and symptoms of this type of disorders, which causes a new position to be proposed and investigated, and includes positive and negative emotional capacity, systems Cognitive systems are information processing systems, arousal regulation systems, and sensorimotor systems (Salis et al., 2020).

The Research Domain Criteria (RDoC) project represents a framework for research on mental disorders that focuses on dimensions of behavioral/psychological functioning and their implementing neural circuits. RDoC originated from one element of the National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH) Strategic Plan for Research released in 2008, a document motivated throughout by the need to accelerate progress in reducing the burden of suffering from mental illness.

Unveiled in 2010, RDoC addresses an emergent obstacle to progress regarding the Institute's mission: the use of traditional diagnostic manuals for research on mental disorders. The primary manual in the United States is the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, currently in its fifth edition (DSM; American Psychiatric Association, 2013).

In fact, the US National Institute of Mental Health created the RDoC as a new framework for research on psychopathology. One of the dimensions that is considered in the diagnostic system of RDoC dimensions to investigate emotional disorders is negative and positive emotional capacity. Positive affective capacity includes valuing, expecting and learning rewards and reinforcement factors. And negative emotional capacity also includes most cases related to disappointment, lack of experience of reward and reinforcement, worries and traumas. Negative emotion reflects how much a person feels helpless, angry, irritable and nervous (Abassi et al., 2018). Considering that most people pay attention to their negative and positive emotions when judging their level of marital satisfaction, which indicates that their positive emotions prevail over negative emotions (Momini, Kerami and Hovizadegan, 2017), hence the study Positive and

negative emotions are very important as indicators of positive and negative activity and may be considered as one of the predictors of marital life satisfaction. On the other hand, RDoC, which is based on analytical research in the fields of neuroscience, genomics and experimental psychology, describes the symptoms and signs of psychopathology, instead of grouping disorders, which was previously done with ICD-11 and DSM-5. Identifying these signs and symptoms can lead to better understanding of emotional disorders and their antecedents based on the RDoC system, compared to DSM-5 and ICD-11. RDoC attempts to overcome some limitations by taking a new approach to the study of brain and behavioral processes that enable a wide range of natural and traumatic experiences to occur in certain environmental contexts (Gore and Widger, 2018). According to studies, the processing of negative emotions in different parts of the brain such as the amygdala in people with emotional disorders are very similar to each other (Planaripol, Pederson and Holtz, 2019). As they try to avoid various emotional experiences, these people make their distress more stable and stable. Positive and negative emotional capacity are probably biological vulnerability factors in the development of emotional disorders. The higher the emotional capacity of a person, the higher the probability of predicting emotional disorders. Also, the low level of positive emotion in a person will increase the occurrence of psychological problems such as depression and social anxiety in him. This shows the importance and relevance of these factors in the emergence of emotional disorders in people.

Considering the high importance of this issue in the society, comprehensive and complete studies have not been conducted in this regard, and it is necessary to investigate the role of these important psychological factors in the occurrence of marital problems. Because knowing the emotional components can play an effective role in improving the psychological condition of couples in the marital relationship; therefore, considering the importance of the emotional components and emotional disorders of couples, the purpose of this research is to investigate the antecedents of emotional disorders of couples on the verge of divorce according to the RDOC framework. In order to achieve this goal, the present study tries to answer the following question: "What are the antecedents of emotional disorders of couples on the verge of divorce according to the RDOC framework?".

2. Methodology

The current research is qualitative and the grounded theory approach is used, which is based on the experience of the interviewees that they have acquired throughout their lives. In this method, the collected data go through their evolution until reaching the theory. Data were obtained through in-depth interviews with experts in the field of psychology with the aim of investigating the antecedents of emotional disorders in couples on the verge of divorce based on RDoC. The research community was experts, professors and experts in the field of psychological science and counseling in Tehran. After collecting the data through triangulation, coding was done on three levels. Open,

central and theoretical codes were extracted in relation to the antecedents of emotional disorders of couples on the verge of divorce. Then, the training protocol was extracted from the three-level codes and was again validated by triangulation. Semi-structured interviews with psychology experts continued until the data reached saturation. In this study, the interview reached saturation in the ninth person. The criteria for entering the study were couples who were on the verge of divorce, had at least one year of experience living together, had no other psychological problems such as depression, the reason for their divorce was not addiction, poverty, unemployment, etc., and disorder an emotion was detected in them by the expert. The exit criterion was lack of accuracy and desire to continue the interview.

A semi-structured interview was used to collect data, and the questions were designed according to the general purpose of the research. The researcher is responsible for decoding the answers and classifying them. After measuring the validity of the study by experts in the field of psychology (validity of evaluators), the full text of the interview was implemented. The people participating in this research plan participated in it with full knowledge and filled the written consent form before conducting the interview. The approximate duration of the interview was 45 to 60 minutes, and during the interview, the voice of the interviewee was recorded and analyzed with his knowledge. In these interviews, an attempt was made to observe ethical principles and the principle of confidentiality was observed and raised. Without any hesitation, the experts could withdraw from the plan at any time and stop their cooperation. No cash was received for participating in the interview session, but the researcher considered a small gift in proportion to the efforts in the long sessions as a token of appreciation and compensation for the effort. During the interview, if necessary, notes were taken by the researcher and the voices of the experts were recorded. After completing the interview with the help of the supervisor and consultant, the necessary coding was done using the three-level method. The interview questions are given in table (1).

Table 1.
Interview questions with psychology experts

Positive emotion	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How did couples respond to love in recent years? (reply to reward) 2. How did couples learn to love their spouses? (reward learning) 3. How did couples value their love and relationship? (reward evaluation)
Negative emotion	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How much have the couple been involved in worrying issues such as infidelity, addiction, job loss, etc.? So that for each of them there is a feeling of fear and extreme concern in the relationship. (feeling of acute threat) 2. How much have the couple been involved in chronic disturbing issues such as rejection, lack of affection, lack of attachment and dependence on the previous family, playmate, etc. during the relationship? (Chronic sense of threat) 3. Were the couples disappointed in their love and affection for each other or in their relationship? (disappointment of reward) 4. How much has each couple felt lost? (feeling of loss)

Source: compiled by the author

From the multitude of information obtained from the interviews, the correct concepts or codes were extracted and coding was done. Then by comparing the obtained concepts, similar and different cases were identified and similar cases were placed in one group, which was named as core codes. These categories help the researcher to establish the right relationship between open codes and the formation and explanation of his theoretical process. Finally, the core codes are placed in another class under the title of theoretical codes based on their concepts. In fact, the results are the results of open and axial coding that creates theoretical coding. This process continued until the data was saturated.

The validity of the current research was evaluated and confirmed by experts in the field of psychology. In order to achieve the credibility of the research, the credibility criteria were examined using the method of Lincoln and Guba (1994, cited by Cope 2014). Re-referencing the elements and components and clarifying the steps and processes in order to facilitate the review and understanding of experiences. In the present study, the agreement for the first evaluator in the open, central and theoretical codes obtained was 0.90 and for the second evaluator was 0.95 and the lack of agreement for the first evaluator was 0.10 and for the second evaluator was 0.05. Therefore, the probability of disagreement was equal to 0.005. With these interpretations, the Kappa coefficient of agreement between the two evaluators in the extracted codes according to the formula was equal to 0.85 (the appropriate value of Cohen's Kappa reliability coefficient is above 0.60 (Cohen, 1960).

3. Results

The phase of implementing qualitative data

In this research, the researcher has used the content analysis method (three stages of coding) or the triangulation method to achieve the desired results. The open, central and theoretical codes extracted from the interviews of psychology researchers, along with some sentences of the interviewees, were extracted for the theoretical code of responding to reward, reward learning code, reward valuing code and reward disappointment code. The theoretical code of responding to rewards for example is given in table (2). The open codes in this table are the result of the inferences of the researcher and expert experts and the dissertation supervisor from the interviewees' conversations, which were obtained by the triangulation method and by carefully examining the content of the interview. The obtained open codes were categorized using the triangulation method, which resulted in axial codes. This process of categorization and extraction with triangulation method continued until the core codes were saturated.

Table 2
Table of open and central codes in the theoretical code of response to reward

INTERVIEW	PHRASE	OPEN CODE	AXIAL CODE
3	The psychotherapist suggested a divorce for the couple, but his wife said that he cannot divorce his wife because he loves her.	Correct answer to reward	Correct answer to reward
4	The lady was attracted to her husband from the beginning and was able to make him interested in her very well.		
5	The lady listened well to her husband's heartache.		
6	The lady loved her husband in life.	Failure to respond to rewards	
1	The lady said that my wife does not respond to my love at all.		
2	The man did not know his wife's love language.		
7	The man did not express love and affection due to emotional deprivation.		
8	The man had a caressing weakness and could not satisfy the psychological needs of his wife.		
9	Husband and wife did not support each other emotionally.	Delayed response to reward	
1	The man showed signs of emotional weakness and lack of control, so it took him weeks to express his problem.		
2	The man had a very low emotional intelligence in society, because of this, he understood many things late and needed additional explanations.		
4	When the relationship was degraded, the lady was ready to restore it, but it was too late.	The right saturation of rewards	
3	The lady cared a lot about her husband and even waited for him until late so that they could eat together.		
6	The lady loved her father very much and saw affection from him.		
5	Husband and wife loved each other so much that despite all the conflicts, they could not live without each other.	Lack of reward saturation	Full of rewards
7	The husband always admired his wife for her independence.		
8	Husband and wife never loved each other and never got enough of love		
9	Their married life was over.		
4	There was no love between husband and wife.		

Source: compiled by the author

- *Conceptual model presented in the field of positive and negative affect subscales*

The conceptual model of the current research is presented based on previous researches and based on the conducted interviews in the form of 3 open, central and theoretical codes in picture (1). In this model, the dimensions of positive and negative emotions were expressed in the fields of valuing rewards, responding to rewards, learning rewards, and disappointment with rewards. This model shows that the awareness of these dimensions in the life of each person can prevent the occurrence of emotional disorders in couples. In fact, the lack of awareness of the different dimensions of emotions in married life can create a vicious cycle and continue in the wrong direction. According to the findings of the research, it seems that if a suitable counseling or treatment program is designed and implemented, it is possible to prevent the occurrence of damages caused by the antecedents of emotional disorders such as negative emotions in the married life of couples.

Figure 1.
Conceptual model presented in the field of positive and negative affect subscales

Source: Authors development

4. Discussion

Discussion around the question: What are the antecedents of emotional disorders of couples on the verge of divorce according to the RDoC framework?

Considering that effective communication and expression of emotions is an essential factor in the difference between satisfied and unhappy couples, therefore the researcher has tried to deeply investigate the factors related to emotional disorders, especially the underlying factors of lack of positive emotion and presence of negative emotion. In couples on the verge of divorce, based on the RDoC system, through interviews with experts in the field of psychology;

Discussing the lack of positive affect system in divorcing couples

Related concepts were obtained through open, theoretical and axial coding, and based on them, three theoretical codes for positive emotion, under the title of response to reward, reward learning and reward valuing, and one theoretical code for negative emotion, under the title of disappointment from specific reward. Became Regarding the theoretical code of reward responsiveness, two central codes were extracted with the title 1. Initial response to reward and 2. Saturation with reward.

Primary response code to reward: a person behaves in two ways when faced with a reward; Either he accepts it and responds at the same moment, or he does not respond to it. In fact, the criteria for accepting the value by the individual will be based on his prioritization and choosing a reward from among several rewards with the same value. This prioritization of value is based on positive and negative aspects of reward. Couples with emotional disorders are not able to respond correctly to their emotional and sexual needs due to low marital satisfaction. Also, emotionally, they do not have the ability to communicate properly with the people around them, especially their life partners.

Reward saturation code: This central code states that repeated repetition of a reward situation causes the person to ignore it. In fact, a kind of saturation with the reward occurs in the person, which reduces the effectiveness of the reward in him. In this case, the person responds to the reward, but this response is so weak that it does not have the power to influence the person. In couples with emotional disorders who are on the verge of divorce, they become indifferent to it due to being constantly placed in similar situations of receiving answers.

Regarding the theoretical code of reward valuation, three core codes with the title; 1. Reward probability, 2. Valuation delay and 3. Valuation effort were extracted.

Bonus Probability Code: In this central code, a person is faced with two modes of reward probability and reward probability error. Open coding of some interviews showed that some couples tend to stay in a relationship with the possibility of receiving rewards in the future. That is, the possibility of receiving a reward makes it possible for this group of couples to continue their marital relationship. The possibility of reward can have a positive effect on improving relationships. On the other hand, a group of couples with emotional disorders do not have a correct prediction of reward, and in most cases, the probability of their reward is met with error. According to the open codes of the conducted interviews, couples who have marital discord decide to do this with the possibility that having children can improve their relationship; Or some couples do a favor or service for their spouse with the possibility of receiving mutual rewards. When their expectations are not met, it causes frustration in one of the parties.

Valuation delay code: There are always factors that can act as an obstacle to reach different rewards. The reinforcing value of rewards is lost over time, so a person may

choose a small reward at one point in time regardless of its value, but the same reward will be worthless to him after the passage of time. Based on this, there are two types of valuation in people towards different rewards: positive valuation and negative valuation. People who have high positive affect, their valuation of rewards is positive and does not change over time. But when negative emotion appears in a person, his evaluation of a value that was positive at the beginning becomes negative with the passage of time.

Valuing effort code: When faced with any reinforcing factor, a person values it first. Therefore, a reinforcing factor can have a different value in two people. People have different mental expectations regarding the consequences of their behavior and the reinforcement factors that appear behind the behavior. According to these expectations, people adjust their behavior in a way that leads to a certain reward. Different rewards have different values from the point of view of each person, and this valuation depends on the situation in which they receive it. Therefore, based on the situation of its occurrence, they judge the value of the received reward. According to the open codes obtained from the interviews of the current research, people act in 3 ways in trying to value: 1. They try for internal reward, like a woman who, because of her love for her husband and her life, tried treatment to have children. 2. They strive for external rewards, like a man who asked for help from his wife's family to resolve his marital disputes with his wife. 3. They don't try to value, like couples who ignore each other's kindness and goodness.

Regarding the theoretical code of reward learning, three core codes were extracted with the title 1. Possible reward learning, 2. Learning error and 3. Error habit.

Probabilistic reward learning code: If a reward is given after a response, it will increase the probability of its occurrence and repetition again in the same situation and conditions. If learning is done correctly, it will improve the relationship between couples. For example, psychotherapist trainings lead to the formation of self-leadership and high acceptance in the parties, and they find this ability to manage the problems that have arisen and take steps to solve them. The more positive the results of these teachings, the more likely couples are to repeat them. On the other hand, if there is no effort or desire to learn to manage and solve problems in couples, not only the relationship between them will not improve, but also the number of differences between couples with each other and even with their children will increase.

Learning error code: wrong prediction about an answer can cause wrong decisions and behaviors that are the basis of disorders between couples. For example, a man's bad heart towards his wife causes him to be overly controlling. Or the destructive behavior of one of the couples causes a decrease in affection and unloveliness of the other party. But correctly predicting a result or reward can increase the acceptance of an error or mistake on the part of one of the couples, and the effort to fix or correct it improves the relationship. For example, in one of the theoretical codes from the interview with the couple, a woman saw her life in danger and knew that she was to blame somewhere and that her schema was flawed, so she started to change it.

Error habit code: People wait for encouragement and reward or punishment for their actions and behaviors. This expectation is a kind of habit that is automatically created in a person. Any behavior that is accompanied by a reward will reinforce and repeat it. In interviews with couples on the verge of divorce, the habit of making mistakes is shown in three forms: habit of reward, lack of habit of reward and error of habit of reward. In habit of reward, it was shown that because the lady had received a lot of love and respect in her own family, she treated her husband accordingly. On the other hand, not being

used to rewards, the lady had received a lot of anxiety and worry from her parents in her family environment, and therefore she was constantly anxious and worried in her life together with her husband. In the third case, there was a kind of pretense in the couple's behavior, they were good with each other in the presence of others, but in their privacy, they were constantly affected by the resentment they had towards each other.

Discussing the negative affect system in couples on the verge of divorce

Regarding the negative emotion system, "disappointment from reward" was proposed, which was characterized by two central codes: 1. Self-directed and 2. Environmental-directed. These two central codes included two open codes, 1. Intrinsic reward and frustration from intrinsic reward and 2. Extrinsic reward and frustration from external reward, respectively.

Reward disappointment: People experience reward disappointment when they fail to obtain positive rewards despite persistent effort. Repeating this reaction can cause sadness in these people (Rockville, 2011). In their study, Iraqi et al. (2019) examined the effectiveness of the approach based on acceptance and commitment on reducing emotional dyslexia and frustration of couples applying for divorce and stated in their results that the approach based on acceptance and commitment significantly reduced the level of depression and emotional dyslexia. Reduces in couples applying for divorce. Acceptance and commitment therapy can be considered as an effective treatment to improve the frustration and ataxia of couples applying for divorce by teaching concepts such as identifying values, mindfulness and committed action.

The final pattern is extracted

The pattern extracted from this study showed how underlying factors in the absence of positive affect system act in the formation of marital disputes in couples who have emotional disorders. Therefore, according to the presented model, there will be 3 solutions to increase or decrease the probability of the antecedents of emotional disorders. People who have a correct prediction of the possibility of reward in their life and give an appropriate response to it, will experience a reduction in emotional disorders. This reward can be approved by family, life partner, friend, etc. or the result of interpersonal interaction, and it makes the person get used to receiving these rewards and over time it becomes a value in him. This type of response to reward shows the presence of a positive affective system in a person's lifestyle. On the other hand, the higher the positive emotion in a person's life, the lower the amount of negative emotion.

This reduces the amount of worry, frustration and stress in one's life. All these factors reduce marital disorders and improve their relationships. On the other hand, people who do not receive any reward or encouragement in their life or do not respond to it, somehow in their life they were not used to being encouraged and loved by the people around them, this lifestyle has become a habit in them. Is. These factors make the system of positive emotions fade in the lives of these people and negative emotions take

its place. This reduction in positive emotions and the increase in negative emotions in a person's life has caused the formation of emotional disorders that create the basis for increasing marital differences in couples' relationships.

5. Conclusion

The aim of the present study was to identify the antecedents of emotional disorders and the lack of positive affect system in couples on the verge of divorce, and in those three factors of response to reward, learning reward and valuing reward in positive affect, and one factor of disappointment from reward in negative affect through interviews with Experts in the field of psychology were examined. Reasons for responding to reward included primary response to reward and saturation of reward. Reward learning factors included learning error, error habit, and reward probability learning, and reward valuation factors included reward probability, valuation delay, and valuation effort. On the other hand, regarding the negative emotion which included the disappointment of the reward, it included two factors of disappointment focused on the self and focused on the environment. Each of these themes also includes a series of categories.

The results showed that the low level of positive emotion and the high level of negative emotion in the lives of people with emotional disorders are caused by the lack of reward experience and response to it and the inability to value the reward. People whose negative life features (whether in their family or in their life together with their partner) are more than positive features, have less hope and vitality and feel less valuable. Respect and gratitude increases the level of life satisfaction and happiness, which is absent or very low in people with negative emotions. In fact, the level of disappointment from internal and external rewards in these people causes the formation of emotional disorders throughout their lives, and its antecedents are manifested in their shared life with another person. On the other hand, a high level of positive emotion greatly reduces the possibility of developing emotional disorders in people. Because these people, interacting with others in the family and society, have learned and applied the 3 characteristics of reward learning, reward response and reward valuing in their lives. Therefore, the feeling of being valuable is formed in these people and this positive thinking is also manifested in their common life. According to the results of the present research, it can be said that positive and negative emotions affect a person's behavior.

The reward arouses motivation and passion and positive emotion is created in the person after the behavior that he receives from the person and receives the reward. On the other hand, not receiving reward or punishment causes annoyance and creates negative emotions. Anticipating receiving a reward and responding to it creates a good feeling in a person, and in doing it again, consistency is created and it becomes a habit. These habits and positive valuing of rewards ultimately cause positive emotions and reduce the possibility of emotional disorders and thus marital disputes. On the other hand, negative emotion and unpleasant mood are created due to disappointment of

reward and its continuation causes the formation of emotional disorders in people, the result of which is the manifestation of negative emotion in the common life.

Conducting any study comes with limitations and one of the most important limitations of the present study; there was a lack of qualitative studies in the field of research in Iran and lack of access to some sources. Also, this research was only conducted regarding the negative and positive affect factors of emotional disorders and other factors of RDoC were not considered. Therefore, researchers are suggested to investigate other antecedents of emotional disorders regarding couples on the verge of divorce. Also, the antecedents of emotional disorders in two groups of couples on the verge of divorce and other couples should be compared. It is also suggested to help improve emotional disorders in couples by holding some educational workshops or psychological programs in the media, and to pay more attention to couples' emotional issues in counseling sessions before marriage so that their relationship does not lead to divorce.

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